

Do Malaysian and Nigerian Accounting Standards Produce Similar Earnings Quality for Banks?

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Abstract:

Accounting standards are developed and issued by individual nations through their accounting standard setting bodies for users and preparers of financial statements, investors, commercial enterprises and regulatory agencies of government. Judgement about earnings quality is made based on accounting information contained in the financial statement. Therefore, the objective of this study is to empirically provide an evidence of the impact of Malaysian Financial Reporting Standards (MFRSs) and Nigerian Statement of Accounting Standards (NSASs) on the earnings quality of their respective banking sectors. The period of study is 2007 – 2011 with Malaysian and Nigerian banks constituting the study sample. The Jones model is modified to investigate the quality of earnings in both economies and a comparative analysis of the different country banks related accounting standard is equally made. It was discovered that Malaysian banks exhibit better earnings quality than Nigerian banks. Findings equally show that Malaysian FRSS are IFRSs compliant, thus more detailed, stricter, and contemporary and prescribe clearer rules than Nigerian SASs indicating that though significant relationship exist between accounting standards and banks earnings quality, MFRSs do not produce similar banks earnings quality with NSASs. It is therefore recommended that Nigerian government, standard setters and appropriate regulatory and supervisory bodies should, as a matter of urgency and seriousness embrace the full adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) and ensure compliance with BASEL II requirements.

Key words: Accounting standards, earnings quality, Jones model, MFRSs, NSASs, IFRSs, Banks

Introduction

A key role of accounting standards is to reduce the economy-wide transactions costs of communicating information among various stakeholders, allowing them to make more efficient real decisions and undertake transactions within, outside and between firms (Hail, Leuz & Wysocki, 2009). Though accounting standards impose regulatory and compliance costs, and could increase the barriers to entry into public capital markets (Hail, Leuz & Wysocki, 2009), it is well known that financial reporting outcomes are determined by the interaction between accounting standards, preparers' incentives, regulation, enforcement, and other institutional features of the economy (Jarva & Lantto, 2011; Ball, 2006; Holthausen, 2009).

Prior research investigating managerial discretion in accounting regimes evidenced that the degree of latitude in accounting standard plays some role in determining the quality of financial measures and reports (Ismaila, Zijl & Dunstanb, 2012). Dye & Sunder (2001) affirm that lax IASB standards allow firms more opportunity to manage their earnings, making financial measures and reports less useful to investors. Goncharov & Zimmermann (2006) equally argue that

accounting standards provide different (amount of) accounting choices, and therefore their application may results in earnings of different quality. To Ewert & Wagenhofer (2005) and Barth, Landsman & Lang (2007) higher earnings quality can be achieved by having stricter accounting standards that limit the number of accounting choices and prescribe clearer rules.

However, Sun, Cahan & Emanuel (2011) examining the impact of IFRS adoption on the earnings quality of foreign firms cross-listed in the U.S. from countries that have already adopted IFRS on a mandatory basis find out that earnings quality from the pre- to post-IFRS period is not different for the cross-listed and matched firms. Similarly, Bartov, Goldberg & Kim (2005) find no significant difference in earnings quality, measured by the price-earnings relationship, for a sample of German New Market firms that were allowed to choose between IFRS and U.S. GAAP. Furthermore, the findings of Van der Meulen, Gaeremynck & Willekens (2007) suggest that there is no difference in value relevance between application of IFRS and U.S. GAAP using a similar sample of German firms.

The above studies focusing on multi-industry and sales based manufacturing firms evidence mixed

findings and results on the impact of different accounting standards on the quality of earnings. Though their findings are quite supportive, to our knowledge, no study has investigated the extent to which earnings quality of specific industry – banks varies due to differences between the Malaysian Financial Reporting Standards (MFRSs) and the Nigerian Statement of Accounting Standards (NSASs). This is an important gap in this literature. This study therefore, conjectures that the quality of Malaysian and Nigerian banks earnings computed using accounting information contained in the financial statements prepared within the framework of MFRSs and NSASs are similar.

This study is divided into the following sections. Section one is the introduction. Section two discusses conceptual framework on earnings quality, Jones Model, Malaysia and Nigeria country profile, reasons for choosing the banking sector, Malaysian and Nigerian Accounting Standards Boards (MASB & NASB) and similarities between MFRSs and NSASs. Section three focuses on the research design. Section four is centred on data presentation, analysis and interpretation of results while section five is all about conclusions and possible recommendations.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Earnings Quality

No consensus on the definition of earnings quality, or even on what construct is intended (Vincent, 2004). Pratt (2003) in Mohammady (2012) defines earnings quality as the extent to which reported earnings on the income statement differ from true earnings. Schipper & Vincent (2003) and Vincent (2004) benchmarking for the definition of earnings quality affirmed that earnings quality is the extent to which reported earnings correspond to economic income as defined by Hicks (1939): “The amount that the firm can pay out in dividends (that is, the amount that can be consumed) during a period, while leaving the firm equally well off at the beginning and the end of the period. Higher quality earnings more faithfully represent the features of the firm’s fundamental earnings process that are relevant to a specific decision made by a specific decision-maker (Dechow, Ge & Schrand, 2010) and are more informative and closer to the long run value of the firm (Kirschenheiter & Melumad, 2004.).

Summing up the above definitions and consistent with Vincent (2004) this study concludes that earnings quality may be a transparent summary indicator of the economic and institutional forces operating on the financial reporting process.

In another dimension though the concept of earnings quality is fundamental in accounting and financial economics, there are deep disagreements about how to measure it (Dichev, Graham, Harvey & Rajgopal 2012). While Francis, LaFond, Olsson & Schipper (2003) broadly categorised criteria used to measure earnings quality into market-based and accounting-based, Dichev et al. (2012) gave the list of candidate measures to include: earnings persistence, predictability, asymmetric loss recognition, various forms of benchmark beating, smooth earnings, magnitude of accruals, income-increasing accruals, absolute value of discretionary or abnormal accruals, and the extent to which accruals map into cash flows. Complicating the measurement of earnings quality, archival research cannot satisfactorily parse out the portion of managed earnings from the portion resulting from the fundamental earnings process (Dechow, Ge and Schrand 2010).

Using Jones (1991) modified model, this study measures earnings quality by decomposing total accruals into its normal and abnormal components. The higher the abnormal accruals evidenced by the residual on the Jones model, the poorer the earnings quality and the smaller the residual the better the earnings quality. In addition, consistent with DeAngelo (1986) and Dechow, Sloan & Sweeney (1995) frequent and high change in total accrual is equally indicative of poor earnings quality and vice versa.

2.2 Jones Model

In accounting literature, Jones Model (1991) (extended by Dechow et al., 1995) has been considered as an indicator of the concept of “abnormal accruals” (Mohammady, 2012). It is a direct estimation model because it identifies accounting fundamentals as the determinants of unmanipulated (expected) accruals (Schipper & Vincent, 2003). Jones takes into account changes in revenue and gross property, plant and equipment to control the economic conditions on the accruals level ((Mohammady, 2012). Jones using this model separates abnormal accruals from

normal accruals by regressing total accruals on variables expected to relate to the economic circumstances of the firm (Fleming, 2012). Tianran (2011) affirmed that Jones model is the best approach to detect earnings quality compared to all other methods in the educational circles. The modified Jones Model is found to be superior to other extant methods at the time in detecting abnormal accruals, i.e., discretionary accruals (Sharifah, Nor, Noor & Fatima, 2012, Dechow & Skinner, 2000) and it provides the most powerful test of earnings management compared to Healy, DeAngelo (Dechow et al., 1995).

2.3 Reasons for Choosing the Banking Sector

The Banking Sector has for centuries now formed one of the pillars of economic prosperity, local or foreign. It is one of the important financial pillars of the financial system which plays a vital role in the successful/failure of any economy. The sector is the lifeline of any modern economy (Aziz, 2012; Sharma & Sharma, 2009). The banking sector plays an important role as financial intermediary and is a primary source of financing for the domestic economy and hence, one of the oldest financial intermediaries in the financial system (Sharma & Sharma, 2009; Hanid, Zarkaria, Abd Karim, Abd Wahab, Stabal & Lee, 2007). To Kamau (2011) in any economy, the financial sector is the engine that drives economic growth through efficient allocation of resources to productive units.

Banks' ability to engender micro or global economic growth and development depends on the health, soundness and stability of the sector. Thus the strength of the economy of any country basically hinges on the strength and efficiency of the financial system which, in turn depends on a sound and solvent banking system (Sharma and Sharma, 2009). Proper and efficient functioning through adequate supervision and governance of the financial sector – banking sector- hinges on adequate transparency and accountability being built into reporting practices in the corresponding sub-sectors. In this regard, financial sector vulnerabilities pose great challenges for the conduct of monetary policy (Draghi, 2012).

Despite the overwhelming importance of the banking sector, prior literatures have documented that business firms' managers, including banks

managers, manage their reported earnings for many different purposes (Wahlen, 1994; Collins, Schackelford & Wahlen, 1995; Kanagaretman, Mathieu & Lobo, 2003; Kanagaretman, Lobo & Yang, 2004; Liu & Ryan, 2006). It is against this background, coupled with mixed arguments on the differences in earnings quality due to different accounting standards that this study acquires banking sectors in Malaysia and Nigerian to provide a comparative analysis of the impact of their respective accounting standards on the quality of banks earnings.

2.4 Malaysian and Nigerian Accounting Standards Boards (MASB & NASB)

This study investigates whether MFRSs and NSASs generate similar quality for banks earnings. Empirical examination of this relationship is logical because earnings quality are measured using accounting information contained in the financial statements particularly the income statement prepared in accordance with the provisions of country specific accounting standards. Statements of Accounting Standards are developed and issued by individual nations, national accounting standard setting bodies like the Financial Accounting Standards Board, USA; Accounting Standards Board, UK; Australian Accounting Research Foundation, Australia, etc. for users and preparers of financial statements, investors, commercial enterprises and regulatory agencies of government.

The Malaysian Accounting Standards Board (MASB) is established under the Financial Reporting Act 1997 (the Act) as an independent authority to develop and issue accounting and financial reporting standards in Malaysia. The MASB, together with the Financial Reporting Foundation (FRF), make up the frameworks for financial reporting in Malaysia. These frameworks comprises an independent standard-setting structure with representation from all relevant parties in the standard-setting process, including preparers, users, regulators and the accountancy profession. The MASB is made up of eight (8) members who are appointed by the Minister of Finance. It comprises the Chairman of the MASB, the Accountant-General and six (6) other members who possess knowledge and experience in the matters of financial accounting and reporting, and in one or more of the fields of accountancy, law,

business and finance. In addition, the Minister of Finance has appointed three (3) advisors to the MASB, one each from the Bank Negara Malaysia, the Securities Commission and the Registrar of Companies.

In Nigeria, the development of accounting and accounting standards could be traced to the then Association of Accountants of Nigeria - AAN (now ICAN). The AAN was formed on the 17th of November 1960 and granted official recognition on 28th September 1965, under the Federal Parliament Act number 15 of 1965, to regulate accountancy profession in the country. History suggests that ICAN was responsible for the formation of the Nigerian Accounting Standard Board (NASB) before it was taken over by government, in 1985 (Josiah, Okoye & Adediran, 2013). Thus, the establishment of NASB was a private sector initiative closely associated with the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN). The Nigerian Accounting Standards Board Act of 2003 provided the legal framework under which NASB set accounting standards.

Membership includes representatives of government and other interest groups. Both ICAN and the Association of National Accountants of Nigeria (ANAN) nominate two members to the board. On the 7th June, 2011, The Federal Republic of Nigeria, in its official Gazette No 54, Vol. 98 enacted the FINANCIAL REPORTING COUNCIL OF NIGERIA ACT, 2011 ACT No. 6 - An ACT to repeal the Nigerian Accounting Standards Board Act, No 22 of 2003 and enact the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria charged with the responsibility among other things, developing and publishing accounting and financial reporting standards to be observed in the preparation of financial statement of public entities in Nigeria and for related matters.

2.5 Similarities between MFRSs and NSASs

Comparing the MFRSs title with the NSASs title, the table below summarises likely areas of similarities between the two set of accounting standards.

Table i Similarities between MFRSs and NSASs

MFRSs	NSASs	Title
MFRS 3	SAS 26	Business Combinations
MFRS 4	SAS 16	Insurance Contracts
MFRS 6	SAS 14 & 17	Exploration for and Evaluation of Mineral Resources
MFRS 8	SAS 24	Operating Segments
MFRS 10	SAS 27	Consolidated Financial Statements
MFRS 102	SAS 4	Inventories
MFRS 107	SAS 18	Statement of Cash Flows
MFRS 106	SAS 1	Accounting Policies. Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors
MFRS 110	SAS 6	Events After Reporting Period
MFRS 111	SAS 5	Construction Contracts
MFRS 112	SAS 19	Income Taxes
MFRS 116	SAS 3	Property, Plant and Equipment
MFRS 117	SAS 11	Leases
MFRS 119	SAS 8	Employee Benefits
MFRS 128	SAS 28	Investments in Associates
MFRS 131	SAS 29	Interests in Joint Ventures
MFRS 133	SAS 21	Earnings Per Share
MFRS 134	SAS 30	Interim Financial Reporting
MFRS 137	SAS 23	Provisions, Contingent Liabilities and Contingent Assets
MFRS 138	SAS 31	Intangible Assets
MFRS 140	SAS 13	Investment Property
MFRS 121	SAS 7	The Effects of Changes in Foreign Exchange Rates

Source: Developed for this Study

Despite the above accounting standards heading similarities between the MFRSs and NSASs, there are some peculiar inherent content differences with MFRSs exhibiting overall clearer rules to reduce complexity by clarifying and adding guidance and eliminating internal inconsistencies. These specific content differences were not investigated by this study due to their universality and indirect relationship with the banking sector.

2.6 Malaysia and Nigeria Country Profiles

Malaysia covers an area of 329,847 km² (67th) (127,355 sq mi). Malaysia border countries include: Brunei 381 km, Indonesia 1,782 km, Thailand 506 km. Going by the 2010 census, Malaysia has a population of 28,334,135 of which 72% of total population constitute the urban population. On the other hand, Nigeria covers an area of 923,768sq km (356,669sq mile). It is bounded by Cameroon to the east, Chad to the northeast, Niger to the north, Benin to the west, and Gulf of Guinea on the Atlantic Ocean to the south (Ofem, 2012). Going by the most recent national census held in 2006, Nigeria has a population of over 140 million inhabitants out of which about 48% live in urban centres. While Malaysia is one of the developed countries of the world, Nigeria is one of the emerging economies. There are some fundamental differences between developed and emerging countries as mentioned by Hofstede and Hofstede (2004) that emerging markets are substantially different from developed markets in terms of the institutional, organisational and market aspects of the economy and society.

Fundamentally, accounting standards in developing markets are typically different from those of developed markets, which make it harder for investors to judge the true performance of a firm in an emerging financial market and thus make rational investment decision (Rashid and Islam, 2008). Similarly, supervisory and regulatory authorities are dependent on political interference in the daily execution of supervisory tasks thereby limiting the roles taken by regulatory authorities (Berghe, 2002) resulting to emerging markets having a weaker and less mature capital market with financial systems dominated by banks. In addition, policies adopted toward the banking systems in these countries often severely constrain the behaviour of banks, in a policy syndrome referred to as financial

repression. In many other cases, the banking systems are dominated by government banks (Gibson, 2003; Lins, 2003). Ownership by state governments is also common in many emerging market countries (Claessens, Djankov & Lang, 2000; Shleifer & Vishny, 1997; Thillainathan, 1998); that leads to greater information asymmetry.

3.0 Research Design

Details relating to country specific accounting standards are directly captured from the comparative analysis of the Malaysian Financial Reporting Standards (MFRSs), Nigerian Statement of Accounting Standards (NSASs) and International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) in addition with contacts made with country standing setting bodies.

3.1 Total Accrual

To investigate earnings quality, this study first estimate total accruals and subsequently modifies and employs the Jones model to decompose the total accruals into its discretionary and non-discretionary components. Consistent with Dabor & Adeyemi (2009); Daniel & Paul (2000); Collins & Hribar, (2002); William (2004); Keefe (2012); Ilanit (2007) and Dechow & Ge (2006), this study estimate Total Accruals (TA) using details from cash flow statements and income statements of banks.

$$TA_{jt} = PBTE_{jt} - OCF_{jt} \dots\dots\dots (i)$$

Where

TA_{jt} = Total Accruals of bank j at time t

$PBTE_{jt}$ = Profit before tax and extraordinary items for bank j at time t; and

OCF_{jt} = Operating cash flows taken directly from cash flow statement for bank j at time t.

3.2. Earnings Quality Measure

This study used the following two models to measure the quality of banks earnings:

3.2.1 Decomposition of Total Accruals Approach

Consistent with Mohammady (2012) this study used the direct estimation of abnormal (discretionary) accruals using accounting fundamentals to proxy for earnings quality. This approach relies on accounting fundamentals to

separate accruals into normal and abnormal components using the Jones model. According to Ronen & Yaari (2008) normal accruals (often referred to as expected or non-discretionary accruals) are accruals that “arise from transactions made in the current period that are normal for the bank given its performance level and business strategy, industry conventions, macro-economic events and other economic factors”. And abnormal accruals (or unexpected or discretionary accruals) are accruals that “arise from transactions made or accounting treatments chosen in order to manage earnings”. Abnormal accruals thus reflect earnings management and inverse measurement of earnings quality (Mohammady, 2012).

3.2.2 Changes in Total Accruals Approach

Following DeAngelo (1986) and Dechow et al. (1995) this study equally measures earnings quality and management through changes in total accruals. There is a high correlation between total accruals and unexpected accruals of 80% or more for U.S and Australian data (Dechow, Richardson & Tuna, 2003) with Schipper et al. (2003) affirming that this relationship is an inverse one. Thus, increasing accruals evidences deterioration in earnings quality (Sloan, 1996).

3.3 Jones Model

Clearly, measures of earnings management based on the Jones (1991) model need to be modified for banks or other financial institutions that are not engaged in sales-based businesses (Cohen, Cornett, Marcus & Tehranian, 2011). This study modifies the Jones model by introducing gross earnings (GE) to replace SALE/REV. This is because what sales or revenue is on the financial statement of manufacturing firms are gross earnings to banks. Banks total gross earnings is the sum of interest and similar income, fee and commission income, foreign exchange income, trusteeship income, income from investments, sharia income and other income. In addition, what goods are to manufacturing industry are loans to banking sector. While manufacturing firms sell goods, banks sell loans. Therefore there is every possibility for loans to go bad. Thus, to estimate these variables, the following formula applies:

Gross Earnings (GE) = Interest Income (IINC) + Fee Commissions (FCOM) + Foreign Exchange Income (FOREXINC) + Trusteeship

Income (TINC) + Investments Income (INVINC) + Sharia Income (SHINC) + Other Income (OINC) (ii)

Total Loans (TL) – Non-performing Loans (NPL) = Net Loans (NL) (iii)

Consistent with Dechow, et al. (1995), Net Loan (ΔNL) is introduced to replace ΔREC .

The modified Jones model is given as follows:

$$DAC_{jt} = TA_{jt}/AST_{jt-1} - [a_0 (1/AST_{jt-1}) + a_{1i} (\Delta GE_{jt}/AST_{jt-1} - \Delta NL_{jt}/AST_{jt-1}) + a_{2i} (PPE_{jt}/AST_{jt-1}) + e_{jt} \dots \dots \dots (iv)$$

Where

TA_{jt} is total accruals of bank i calculated as the difference between profit or loss before taxation, exceptional and extraordinary items and operating cash flows for year t ;

AST_{jt-1} is assets at the beginning of the year;

ΔGE_{it} is the change in Gross earnings from year $t-1$ to t ;

ΔNL_{jt} is the change in the analysis of total loans and advances and non-performing loan from year $t-1$ to t to reflect change in Net Loans (ΔNL) replacing change in Receivables (ΔREC); and PPE is gross property, plant, and equipment.

e_{jt} is the error term or residual indicating discretionary accruals.

The introduction of Gross Earnings (GE), Loans and nonperforming loans to reflect net loans is to enable the model investigate discretionary accruals accurately as managers have discretions over accruals accounts and transactions like loans, nonperforming loans, and loan loss provision (Gebhardt & Novotny-Farkas, 2010; Samadi & Valahzaghari, 2013; Marton & Runesson, 2012; Tianran, 2011 and Rolland, 2012).

All variables are deflated by prior year's total assets to reduce the problem of heteroscedasticity consistent with prior studies (Rashidah & Afidah, 2002).

3.4 Study Sample and Period

The sample of this study constitutes banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange Commission and Malaysian Local Commercial banks 2007 to 2011. This study used details of total accruals (TA) obtained by subtracting operating cash flows (OCF) from profit before tax and extra ordinary items (PBTE), gross earnings (GE), total assets (TA), loans and advances, property, plant and equipment (PPE), non-performing loans to investigate earnings quality for the period of study using the modified Jones model. Accounting

standards details were directly captured comparatively from the Malaysian Financial Reporting Standards (MFRSs), International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) and the Nigerian Statement of Accounting Standards (NSASs) in addition with consultation with the country respective accounting standards setting boards.

4.0 Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Sequel to the fact that this study provides a comparative study of accounting standards and banks earnings quality: Malaysian and Nigerian journey until now and road ahead, it is worthy to note that the findings of this study indicate opposite results in terms of variables values, practical situations and framework of accounting standards for both samples affirming the fundamental dichotomies in their economies and the reasons for the differences in their earnings quality. These findings are discussed in the following section.

4.1 Earnings Quality Decomposition of Total Accruals

The absolute value of abnormal accruals ($|AA_{jt}|$) is the measure of earnings quality with lower values indicating higher earnings quality. A common measure of earnings management in industrial firms is based on discretionary accruals

from the modified Jones (1991) model (Dechow, et al., 1995). Specifically, “normal” accruals were estimated from a simple statistical model based on firm assets, property, plant and equipment, and change in gross earnings (GE) and net loans (NL). “Abnormal” or discretionary accruals are the residuals between actual accruals and the predicted accruals from the modified Jones model. Residual statistics and analysis of variance are provided in table ii, iii and iv. The high residual value in the equation (e) for Nigerian banks is 1.94782 which means that there exist a weak relationship between the independent and dependent variables evidencing poor quality of accruals and earnings for Nigerian banks. The higher the value of (e), the weaker the relationship between total accruals (TACC), gross earnings (GE), net loans (NL) and property, plant and equipment (PPE). On the other hand, the residual for Malaysian banks is 0.075062 evidencing a stronger association between these variables, thereby indicating high accrual and earnings quality. In addition, Nigerian banks have -0.97546 and 0.49718 representing respectively minimum and maximum residuals and with a median of 0.03385. Conversely, Malaysian banks exhibit respectively minimum and maximum residual values of -0.132780 and 0.082327, having a median of 0.004758.

Table ii Residuals Statistics

	Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
Malaysian banks	-0.132780	-0.031928	0.004758	0.034110	0.082327
Nigerian banks	-0.97546	-0.05150	0.03385	0.07218	0.49718

Table iii Analysis of Variance Table for Nigerian Banks

	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
X1	1	0.01198	0.011976	0.3136	0.577949
X2	1	0.00443	0.004427	0.1159	0.734914
X3	1	0.27513	0.275129	7.2037	0.009787
Residuals	51	1.94782	0.038193		

Signif codes: 0 ‘***’ 0.001 ‘**’ 0.01 ‘*’ 0.05 ‘.’ 0.1 ‘.’ 1

Table iv Analysis of Variance Table for Malaysian Banks

	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
X1	1	0.000234	0.00023363	0.0871	0.7700
X2	1	0.001162	0.00116155	0.4333	0.5158
X3	1	0.000351	0.00035121	0.1310	0.7201
Residuals	28	0.075062	0.00268077		

Signif codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Table v Coefficients for Malaysian Banks:

	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-9.817e-03	4.190e-02	-0.234	0.816
X1	-2.273e+05	9.440e+05	-0.241	0.811
X2	-2.826e-02	6.928e-02	-0.408	0.686
X3	2.639e+00	7.291e+00	0.362	0.720

Signif codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.05178 on 28 degrees of freedom

Multiple R-squared: 0.02274, Adjusted R-squared: -0.08197

F-statistics: 0.2171 on 3 and 28 DF, p-value: 0.8837

Table vi Coefficients for Nigerian Banks:

	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.0790	0.0341	-2.317	0.02457*
X1	15025.6798	30523.5351	0.492	0.62464
X2	0.1496	0.1712	0.874	0.38648
X3	0.3289	0.1226	2.684	0.00979**

Signif codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.1954 on 51 degrees of freedom

Multiple R-squared: 0.1302, Adjusted R-squared: 0.07902

F-statistics: 2.544 on 3 and 51 DF, p-value: 0.06633

4.2 Changes in Total Accrual as Measure of Earnings quality

In another dimension, changes in total accrual are equally indicative of earnings quality. The significant change in the total accruals (Y) for Nigeria banks is an indicator that these banks are

engaged in earnings management with its consequential effect of deteriorating earnings quality. As provided in table vii, Nigerian banks exhibit higher variance for all the variables with X1, X2 X3 and Y respectively having 7.649640e-13, 2.530170e-02, and 4.920363e-02 and 4.146943e-02 values compared to 1.220234e-16, 2.430964e-02, 2.291071e-06 and 2.477676e-03 for Malaysian banks. The low quality of accruals

as evidenced by a high value of the residual for Nigerian banks indicates higher standard deviation of 8.746222e-07, 0.1590651, 0.2218189 and 0.2036404 respectively for variables x1, x2, x3 and y while Malaysian banks higher quality of accruals suggest lower standard deviations and variability of 1.104642e-08, 0.1559155, 0.001513628 and 0.04977625 for the same variables.

Table vii Variables Standard Deviation and Variances - Accrual Analysis

Malaysian Banks

	x1	x2	x3	y
Variable var	1.220234e-16	0.02430964	2.291071e-06	0.002477676
Variable sd	1.104642e-08	0.1559155	0.001513628	0.04977625

Nigerian Banks

	x1	x2	x3	y
Variable var	7.649640e-13	0.0253017	0.04920363	0.04146943
Variable sd	8.746222e-07	0.1590651	0.2218189	0.2036404

4.3 Banks Related Standards that Accord MFRSs Superiority Over the NSASs

Though MFRSs are issued by the MASB in respect of its application in Malaysia, these standards contain materials in which the IFRS Foundation holds copyright and which have been

reproduced in these Standards with the permission of the IFRS Foundation. The material, fundamental but significant topical differences between the Nigerian SASs and Malaysian FRSs as it relates to the banking sector is tabulated below:

Table viii Banks related Standards Differences between MFRSs and NSASs

S/no	Malaysian FRSs	Nigerian SASs
1	MFRS 7- Financial Instruments: Disclosures	SAS 10-Accounting by Banks and Non-Bank Financial Institutions Part I
2	MFRS 9- Financial Instruments	SAS 15-Accounting by Banks and Non-Bank Financial Institutions Part II
3	MFRS -13 Fair Value Measurement	
4	MFRS-132 Financial Instruments: Presentation	
5	MFRS-139 Financial Instruments: Recognition and Measurement	

Source: Developed for this study

The enactment of MFRS 7 which is equivalent to IFRS 7 (Financial Instruments: Disclosures) is consequent upon the fact that IASB concluded

that there was a need to revise and enhance the disclosures in IAS 30 Disclosures in the Financial Statements of Banks and Similar Financial

Institutions and IAS 32 Financial Instruments: Disclosure and Presentation. In the light of this revision, the Nigerian SAS 10 and 15 (Accounting by Banks and Non-Bank Financial Institutions Part I & II) are rendered obsolete.

Outside banks related accounting standards (MFRSs 7, 9, 13, 132 and 139) that accord MFRSs greater superiority over NSASs this study equally discovered the following differences as tabulated below:

4.4 Other Areas of Differences between MFRSs and NSASs

Table ix Other Areas of Differences between Country Accounting Standards

S/no	Malaysian FRSs	Nigerian SASs
1	MFRS1- first time adoption of MFRSs and government loans	SAS 2- information to be disclosed in financial statements
2	MFRS 2- share based payment	SAS 9- accounting for depreciation
3	MFRS5- non-current assets held for sale and discontinued operations	SAS 12- accounting for deferred taxes
4	MFRS11- joint arrangements	SAS 20- abridged financial statements
5	MFRS12- disclosure of interests in other entities	SAS 22- research and development costs
6	MFRS101- presentations of financial statements and presentation of items of other comprehensive income	SAS 25- telecommunication activities
7	MFRS116-revenue	SAS 32- accounting by not-for-profit organisation
8	MFRS120- accounting for government grants and disclosure of government assistants	
9	MFRS123- borrowing costs	
10	MFRS124- related party disclosures	
11	MFRS126- accounting and reporting by retirement benefit plans	
12	MFRS127- consolidated and separate financial statements	
13	MFRS129- financial reporting in hyperinflationary economies	
14	MFRS136- impairment of assets	
15	MFRS141- agriculture	

Source: Developed for this study

4.5 The Place of IFRSs

The assets and liabilities of financial institutions are majorly financial instruments. Thus financial institutions have many financial instruments as against manufacturing entities that have few financial instruments in the form of account receivable and account payable. The above five accounting standards that accord the MFRSs

superiority over the NSASs in relation to banks are specifically on financial instruments. These standards as earlier noted are rooted in the IFRSs and consistent with their IFRSs equivalent, these standards apply to all risks arising from all financial instruments. The objectives of these standards and their respective IFRSs equivalent are depicted in the table below:

Table x Objective and IFRSs Equivalents of Standards that Accord Reasonable MFRSs Superiority over NSASs

MFRS Code	MFRS Topic	MFRS Objective(s)	MFRS/IFRS Equivalent
MFRS 7	Financial Instruments: Disclosures	to provide disclosures in their financial statements that enable users to evaluate: (a) the significance of financial instruments for the entity's financial position and performance; and (b) the nature and extent of risks arising from financial instruments to which the entity is exposed during the period and at the end of the reporting period, and how the entity manages those risks.	IFRS 7
MFRS 9	Financial Instruments	to establish principles for the financial reporting of financial assets that will present relevant and useful information to users of financial statements for their assessment of the amounts, timing and uncertainty of the entity's future cash flows.	IFRS 9
MFRS 13	Fair Value Measurement	This MFRS: (a) defines fair value; (b) sets out in a single MFRS a framework for measuring fair value; and (c) requires disclosures about fair value measurements.	IFRS 13
MFRS 132	Financial Instruments: Presentation	to establish principles for presenting financial instruments as liabilities or equity and for offsetting financial assets and financial liabilities	IAS 32
MFRS 139	Financial Instruments: Recognition and Measurement	to establish principles for recognising and measuring financial assets, financial liabilities and some contracts to buy or sell non-financial items	IAS 39

Source: Developed for this Study

The harmonised and synchronised objective of these standards giving consideration to disclosure of qualitative and quantitative information about exposure to risks arising from financial instruments, including specified minimum disclosures about credit risk, liquidity risk and market risk and the principles for recognising, measuring and presenting financial assets and financial liabilities is to present and provide relevant and useful information to users of financial statements for their assessment of the financial position and financial performance and the amounts, timing and uncertainty of an entity's future cash flows. Consequentially, the provisions vis-à-vis the objectives of these MFRSs borders on transparent, timely and accurate reporting of earnings.

4.6 Basel II Compliance

Basel II is the second of the Basel Accords, (now extended and effectively superseded by Basel III), which are recommendations on banking laws and regulations issued by the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision. Fundamentally, while no bank in Nigeria adopt Basel II as global standards, all banks in Malaysian adopted Basel II in line with the directive from Bank Negara Malaysia ('BNM'). The Basel II framework is structured around three fundamental Pillars.

- Pillar 1 defines the minimum capital requirement to ensure that financial institutions hold sufficient capital to cover their exposure to credit, market and operational risks.

- Pillar 2 requires financial institutions to have a process for assessing their overall capital adequacy in relation to their risk profile and a strategy for maintaining their capital levels.

- Pillar 3 requires financial institutions to establish and implement an appropriate disclosure policy that promotes transparency regarding their risk management practices and capital adequacy positions.

4.7 The Missing Link in NSASs

Banks including Nigerian banks have assets and liabilities in the form of financial instruments. There are no clear, comprehensive and contemporary NSASs on the disclosure of qualitative and quantitative information about exposure to risks arising from financial instruments. SAS 10 and SAS 15 (Accounting by Banks and Non-Bank Financial Institutions Part I & II) are grossly deficient in influencing users' assessment of the financial position and financial performance of banks or the amounts, timing and uncertainty of banks future cash flows in the light of globalisation in accounting standards and current economic reality. Lack of principles for recognition, measurement and presentation of information about financial assets and liabilities (financial instruments) are likely responsible for the poor earnings quality for Nigeria banks, thus the missing link.

In addition, non-compliance with Basel II requirements which ensure that financial institutions hold sufficient capital to cover their exposure to credit, market and operational risks and the implementation of an appropriate disclosure policy that promotes transparency regarding their risk management practices and capital adequacy positions is another issue that calls for the urgent attention of both regulatory and supervisory bodies.

5.0 Conclusions and Recommendations

The earnings quality were calculated using accounting information and fundamentals as contained in the financial statements of banks prepared in accordance with MFRSs for Malaysian banks and NSASs for Nigerian banks and with the aid of the modified Jones model in decomposing total accrual into its discretionary and non-discretionary components, the residuals

of the model indicating accruals and earnings quality was higher for Nigerian banks than Malaysian banks. This result is traced to the fact that the Malaysian Financial Reporting Standards that relates to the preparing of banks financial statements have their equivalents in the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) consequently according the bank related MFRSs superior edge over the NSASs otherwise described as obsolete.

This study therefore concludes that MFRSs and NSASs produce different earnings quality for their banks suggesting that there exist significant relationship between differences in accounting standards and varying quality of banks earnings. This study recommends that Nigerian government, standard setters and appropriate regulatory and supervisory bodies should, as a matter of urgency and seriousness embrace the full adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) and ensure compliance with BASEL II requirements.

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